

On the F_3 -domination number of generalized Petersen graphs $P(n, 1)$ and $P(n, 2)$

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A B S T R A C T

Let G be a graph with the vertex set $V(G)$. G is called 2-stratified if $V(G)$ is partitioned into red and blue vertices. The stratified domination number of a graph G is the minimum number of red vertices of $V(G)$ in a red-blue coloring of the vertices of $V(G)$ such that every blue vertex v of $V(G)$ lies in a vuw (blue, blue, red) path in G for a blue vertex $u \in V(G)$ ($u \neq v$) and a red vertex $w \in V(G)$. In this paper we study the stratified domination number of generalized Petersen graphs $P(n, 1)$ for $n \geq 3$ is an integer and $P(n, 2)$ for $n \geq 6$ is an even integer. We prove that for $n \geq 3$,

$$\gamma_F(P(n, 1)) = 2 \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil$$

and for $n \geq 6$,

$$\gamma_F(P(n, 2)) = \begin{cases} 4 \left\lceil \frac{n}{12} \right\rceil, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, \\ 4 \left\lfloor \frac{n+2}{12} \right\rfloor + 2, & \text{if } n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

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Stratified domination, 2-stratified graphs, F_3 -domination, generalized Petersen graphs.

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1 Introduction

Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a finite, undirected, simple graph. The subset $S \subseteq V(G)$ is a *dominating set* of G if each vertex in $V(G) - S$ is adjacent to at least one vertex in S . The *domination number of G* , denoted by $\gamma(G)$, is the cardinality of a minimum dominating set of G . A minimum dominating set of G is a $\gamma(G)$ -*set*. Domination in graphs and its variations have been well studied in the literature, see the books by Haynes, Hedetniemi and Slater [5, 6]. A set $S \subseteq V(G)$ is a *total dominating set* if every vertex $v \in V(G)$ has at least one neighbor in S . The *total domination number* $\gamma_t(G)$ is the minimum cardinality of a total dominating set. A set $S \subseteq V(G)$ is a *restrained dominating set* if every vertex $v \in V(G) - S$ has at least one neighbor in S . The *restrained domination number* $\gamma_r(G)$ is the minimum cardinality of a restrained dominating set. A set $S \subseteq V(G)$ is a *k -dominating set* if every vertex $v \in V(G)$ has at least k neighbor in S . The *k -domination number* $\gamma_k(G)$ is the minimum cardinality of a k -dominating set.

Dividing the vertex set of a graph into classes according to some prescribed rule is a fundamental process in graph theory. Rashidi [1] defined a graph G to be a stratified graph if its vertex set is partitioned into classes. A graph $G = (V(G), E(G))$ together with a fixed partition of its vertex set $V(G)$ into nonempty subsets is called a stratified graph. If the partition is $V(G) = \{V_1, V_2\}$, then G is a 2-stratified graph and the sets V_1 and V_2 are called the strata or sometimes the color classes of G . We ordinarily color the vertices of V_1 red and the vertices of V_2 blue. Rashidi [1] studied a number of problems involving stratified graphs; while distance in stratified graphs was investigated in [2, 3]. The study of combining stratification and domination in graphs was started by Chartrand, Haynes, Henning and Zhang [4]. Let F be a 2-stratified graph with one fixed blue vertex v specified. We say that F is rooted at the blue vertex v . An F -coloring of a graph G is defined in [4] to be a red-blue coloring of the vertices of G such that every blue vertex v of G belongs to a copy of F (not necessarily induced in G) rooted at v . The F -domination number $\gamma_F(G)$ of G is the minimum number of red vertices of G in an F -coloring of G . In [4], an F -coloring of G that colors $\gamma_F(G)$ vertices red is called a γ_F -coloring of G . The set of red vertices in a γ_F -coloring is called a γ_F -set. If G has order n and G has no copy of F , then certainly $\gamma_F(G) = n$. See [7–18] for further studies on F -domination.

If F is a K_2 rooted at a white vertex v adjacent to a black vertex, then F -domination is the same as the usual domination. Hence, $\gamma(F) = \gamma_F(G)$. For the case when F is a P_3 , there are five 2-stratified graphs, see Fig. 1.

Figure 1: The five 2-stratified paths P_3

It was proved in [4] that for any connected graph G of at least three vertices, (i) $\gamma_{F_1}(G) = \gamma_t(G)$, (ii) $\gamma_{F_2}(G) = \gamma(G)$, (iii) $\gamma_{F_4}(G) = \gamma_r(G)$, and (iv) $\gamma_{F_5}(G) = \gamma_2(G)$. The parameter γ_{F_3} appears to be new. It then was studied in the literature. It was shown that the concept of F_3 -domination is different from the 2-(step) domination [4]. All the results so far except from two last articles are on upper and lower bounds and exact values for special graphs [8, 9, 11, 13–15]. In [19], it was shown that the F_3 -domination problem is NP-complete for bipartite planar graphs and for chordal graphs. And also given a linear-time algorithm for the F_3 -domination problem in trees. In [20], F_3 -domination number was calculated for the Cartesian product of some special graph classes such as cycles and paths. Also a new definition of F_3 -domination which is related to distance was given in [20]. For convenience we use *stratified domination* and F_3 -domination in the same meaning. Since all the parameters except F_3 -domination equals the other domination parameters.

The generalized Petersen graph $P(n, k)$ is the graph with vertex set $V(P(n, k)) = U \cup W$, where $U = \{u_i : 0 \leq i \leq n - 1\}$ and $W = \{w_i : 0 \leq i \leq n - 1\}$, and edge set $E(P(n, k)) = \{u_i u_{i+1}, u_i w_i, w_i w_{i+k} : 0 \leq i \leq n - 1, \text{subscripts modulo } n\}$. The domination number of generalized Petersen graphs has been well studied in graph theory. In recent years, there have been many results on generalized Petersen graphs and related to domination parameters. See [21–25] and references therein. The stratified domination number of the generalized Petersen graphs has not been studied in the literature so far. In this paper we study the stratified domination number of generalized Petersen graphs $P(n, 1)$ and $P(n, 2)$.

2 The stratified domination number of $P(n, 1)$ and $P(n, 2)$

In this section we compute the stratified domination number of the generalized Petersen graphs.

Theorem 1. For any positive integer $n \geq 3$, $\gamma_{F_3}(P(n, 1)) = 2 \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$.

Proof. The result is straightforward to verify for $n \leq 5$. Assume then that $n \geq 6$. We show first that there exists an F_3 -coloring of $P(n, 1)$ that colors $u_1, u_6, \dots, u_{1+5 \lfloor \frac{n-1}{5} \rfloor}$ and $w_1, w_6, \dots, w_{1+5 \lfloor \frac{n-1}{5} \rfloor}$ red. Let the set $S = \{u_1, u_6, \dots, u_{1+5 \lfloor \frac{n-1}{5} \rfloor}, w_1, w_6, \dots, w_{1+5 \lfloor \frac{n-1}{5} \rfloor}\}$ show the red vertices of this F_3 -coloring of $P(n, 1)$. Consider this F_3 -coloring of $P(n, 1)$. Notice that every blue vertex lies in a blue-blue-red path in $P(n, 1)$ (see Fig.2). Therefore, $\gamma_{F_3}(P(n, 1)) \leq 2 \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$.

And now we show that $\gamma_{F_3}(P(n, 1)) \geq 2 \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$ for any positive integer $n \geq 6$. We proceed by induction on the order n . If $n = 6$, the claim is trivial. Let accept that the claim is true for $n \geq 6$. We show that the claim is true for $n + 1$. We know that the set $S = \{u_1, u_6, \dots, u_{1+5 \lfloor \frac{n-1}{5} \rfloor}, w_1, w_6, \dots, w_{1+5 \lfloor \frac{n-1}{5} \rfloor}\}$ is an F_3 -dominating set of $P(n, 1)$. We must add 2 extra vertex to $P(n, 1)$ for to acquire $P(n + 1, 1)$. For $n \equiv 1, 2, 3, 4 \pmod{5}$ the new adding two blue vertex have been already lied in a blue-blue-red path in $P(n + 1, 1)$. Therefore $\gamma_{F_3}(P(n + 1, 2)) = \gamma_{F_3}(P(n, 2))$ for $n \equiv 1, 2, 3, 4 \pmod{5}$. Hence $\gamma_{F_3}(P(n + 1, 2)) \geq 2 \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil = 2 \lceil \frac{n+1}{5} \rceil$ for $n \equiv 1, 2, 3, 4 \pmod{5}$. For $n \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ the new adding two vertex must be colored red to preserve u_n and w_n lies in a blue-blue-red path in $P(n + 1, 1)$. Therefore

Figure 2: The minimum F_3 domination in $GP(15, 1)$

$\gamma_{F_3}(P(n+1, 2)) = \gamma_{F_3}(P(n, 2)) + 2$ for $n \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. Hence $\gamma_{F_3}(P(n+1, 2)) \geq 2 \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil + 2 = 2 \lceil \frac{n+1}{5} \rceil$ for $n \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. So the proof is completed. $\square$

And now we begin to compute the F_3 -domination number in $P(n, 2)$ for $n \geq 6$ even integers. For convenience we prefer to show $P(n, 2)$ as the form of three cycles one within the other. The outer cycle denoted by W_o which is consists of the vertices $w_1, w_3, \dots, w_{n-1}$ and the inner cycle denoted by W_i which is consists of the vertices $w_2, w_4, \dots, w_n$ for n is even. The middle cycle consists of the vertices of U . Since $P(n, 2)$ is not planar for odd integers, if n is odd this representation is not valid.

Theorem 2. For any positive even integer $n \geq 6$,

$$\gamma_F(P(n, 2)) = \begin{cases} 4 \lceil \frac{n}{12} \rceil, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, \\ 4 \lfloor \frac{n+2}{12} \rfloor + 2, & \text{if } n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

Proof. There are two cases.

Case 1: Let $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. We show first that there exists an F_3 -coloring of $P(n, 2)$ that colors $w_1, w_7, \dots, w_{n-14}, w_{n-7}, w_{n-1}$ (the vertices of W_o) and $w_2, w_8, \dots, w_{n-6}, w_n$ (the vertices of W_i) red. Consider this F_3 -coloring of $P(n, 2)$. Notice that all the blue vertices of $P(n, 2)$ lie in a blue-blue-red path in $P(n, 2)$ (see Fig.3). Therefore $\gamma_F(P(n, 2)) \leq 4 \lceil \frac{n}{12} \rceil$.

And now we show that $\gamma_F(P(n, 2)) \geq 4 \lceil \frac{n}{12} \rceil$. We proceed by induction on the order n . If $n = 8$, the claim is trivial. Let accept that the claim is true for $n \geq 8$. We show that the claim is true for $n+4$. We know that the set $S = \{w_1, w_7, \dots, w_{n-14}, w_{n-7}, w_{n-1}, w_2, w_8, \dots, w_{n-6}, w_n\}$ is an F_3 -dominating set of $P(n, 2)$. We must add 4 extra vertex to $P(n, 2)$ for to acquire $P(n+4, 2)$. Note that the new adding blue vertices have been already lied in

Figure 3: The minimum F_3 domination in $GP(20, 2)$ for the Case 1 of Theorem 3

a blue-blue-red path in $P(n + 4, 2)$. Therefore $\gamma_{F_3}(P(n + 4, 2)) = \gamma_{F_3}(P(n, 2))$. Hence $\gamma_{F_3}(P(n + 6, 2)) \geq 4 \lceil \frac{n}{12} \rceil = 4 \lceil \frac{n+4}{12} \rceil$. So the proof is completed.

Case 2: Let $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$. We show first that there exists an F_3 -coloring of $P(n, 2)$ that colors $w_1, w_7, \dots, w_{n-11}, w_{n-5}$ (the vertices of W_o) and $w_2, w_8, \dots, w_{n-4}$ (the vertices of W_i) red. Consider this F_3 -coloring of $P(n, 2)$. Notice that all the blue vertices of $P(n, 2)$ lie in a blue-blue-red path in $P(n, 2)$ (see Fig.4). Therefore $\gamma_F(P(n, 2)) \leq 4 \lfloor \frac{n+2}{12} \rfloor + 2$.

And now we show that $\gamma_F(P(n, 2)) \geq 4 \lfloor \frac{n+2}{12} \rfloor + 2$. We proceed by induction on the order n . If $n = 6$, the claim is trivial. Let accept that the claim is true for $n \geq 6$. We show that the claim is true for $n+4$. We know that the set $S = \{ w_1, w_7, \dots, w_{n-11}, w_{n-5}, w_2, w_8, \dots, w_{n-10}, w_{n-4} \}$ is an F_3 -dominating set of $P(n, 2)$. We must add 4 extra vertex to $P(n, 2)$ for to acquire $P(n+4, 2)$. Note that the new adding blue vertices have been already lied in a blue-blue-red path in $P(n + 4, 2)$. Therefore $\gamma_{F_3}(P(n + 4, 2)) = \gamma_{F_3}(P(n, 2))$. Hence $\gamma_{F_3}(P(n + 6, 2)) \geq 4 \lfloor \frac{n+2}{12} \rfloor + 2 = 4 \lfloor \frac{n+6}{12} \rfloor + 2$. So the proof is completed. $\square$

3 Conclusion

In this study we compute F_3 -domination number of generalized Petersen graphs $P(n, 1)$ and $P(n, 2)$ for even integers. Computing F_3 -domination number of generalized Petersen graphs $P(n, 2)$ for odd integers is an open problem. It can be interesting to study F_3 -domination number of generalized Petersen graphs $P(n, 3)$, $P(n, 4)$ and $P(n, k)$ for further studies.

Figure 4: The minimum F_3 domination in $GP(18, 2)$ for the Case 2 of Theorem 3

References

- [1] R. Rashidi, The Theory and Applications of Stratified Graphs (Ph.D. Dissertation, Western Michigan University, 1994).
- [2] G. Chartrand, H. Gavlas, M.A. Henning and R. Rashidi, Stratidistance in stratified graphs, *Math. Bohem.* 122 (1997) 337-347.
- [3] G. Chartrand, L. Holley, R. Rashidi, N.A. Sherwani, Distance in stratified graphs, *Czech. Math. J.* 125 (2000) 135-146.
- [4] G. Chartrand, T.W. Haynes, M.A. Henning, P. Zhang, Stratification and domination in graphs, *Discrete Math.* 272 (2003) 171-185.
- [5] T.W. Haynes, S.T. Hedetniemi, P.J. Slater, *Fundamentals of Domination in Graphs*, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1998.
- [6] T.W. Haynes, S.T. Hedetniemi, P.J. Slater (Eds.), *Domination in Graphs: Advanced Topics*, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1998.
- [7] G. Chartrand, T.W. Haynes, M.A. Henning, P. Zhang, Stratified claw domination in prisms, *J. Combin. Math. Combin. Comput.* 33 (2000) 81-96.
- [8] R. Gera, P. Zhang, Bounds for the F-domination number of a graph, *Congr. Numer.* 166 (2004) 131-144.
- [9] R. Gera, P. Zhang, Realizable triples for stratified domination in graphs, *Math. Bohem.* 130 (2005) 185-202.
- [10] R. Gera, P. Zhang, On stratified domination in oriented graphs, *Congr. Numer.* 173 (2005) 175-192.

- [11] R. Gera, P. Zhang, On stratification and domination in graphs, *Discuss. Math. Graph Theory* 26 (2006) 249-272.
- [12] R. Gera, P. Zhang, Stratified domination in oriented graphs, *J. Combin. Math. Combin. Comput.* 60 (2007) 105-125.
- [13] M.A. Henning, J.E. Maritz, Stratification and domination in graphs II, *Discrete Math.* 286 (2004) 203-211.
- [14] M.A. Henning, J.E. Maritz, Stratification and domination in graphs with minimum degree two, *Discrete Math.* 301 (2005) 175-194.
- [15] M.A. Henning, J.E. Maritz, Stratification and domination in graphs with minimum degree two, *Discrete Math.* 301 (2005) 175-194.
- [16] M.A. Henning, J.E. Maritz, Stratification and domination in prisms, *Ars Combin.* 81 (2006) 343-358.
- [17] M.A. Henning, J.E. Maritz, Simultaneous stratification and domination in graphs with minimum degree two, *Quaest. Math.* 29 (2006) 1-16.
- [18] T.W. Haynes, M.A. Henning, P. Zhang, A survey of stratified domination in graphs, *Discrete Math.* 309 (2009) 5806-5819.
- [19] G. J. Chang, C. W. Chang, D. Kuo, S.H. Poon, Algorithmic aspect of stratified domination in graphs, *Information Processing Letters* 113 (2013) 861-865
- [20] C. W. Chang, D. Kuo, S.C. Liaw and J.H. Yan, F_3 -domination problems in graphs, *Journal of Combinatorial Optimization* 28 (2014) 400-413.
- [21] J. Liu, X. Zhang, The exact domination number of generalized Petersen graphs, *Comp. Appl. Math.* (2014) 33:497-506.
- [22] W. S. Li, H.M. Xing, M. Y. Sohn, On the signed total domination number of generalized Petersen graphs $P(n, 2)$, *Bull. Korean Math. Soc.* 50 (2013) 2021-2026.
- [23] X. Fu, Y. Yang, B. Jiang, On the domination number of generalized Petersen graphs $P(n, 2)$, *Discrete Mathematics* 309 (2009) 2445-2451.
- [24] H. Wang, X. Xu, Y. Yang, K. Lü, Liar's domination number of generalized Petersen graphs $P(n, 1)$ and $P(n, 2)$, *Util. Math.* 82 (2012) 317-335.
- [25] R. Barrera, D. Ferrero, Power domination in cylinders, tori, and generalized Petersen graphs, *Networks* 58 (2011) 43-49.